

FAIR4RS

Research Software Definition workshop

Collaborative notes - 23 February 2021 - Second meeting

21:00 CEST

Useful links

[RDA group page](#),

[GitHub repository](#)

[Gitter chat](#)

[Subgroup3 document \(collection of quotes, collection of example\)](#)

Agenda

00:00	Welcome & introductions
00:05	The concept of an "inclusive" vs. "exclusive" definition
00:35	Software examples to complete report's case study
01:10	The "chicken or the egg dilemma" of software in a scholarly infrastructure
01:25	Conclusion and next steps (proceeding with the output)

Participants in 2nd meeting

- **Add your name, institution, job title, country, member, if want to participate actively in the output production**

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<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-4-research-software-fair4rs-wg>

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If you have provided this information in the past just add your name and ORCID

Name + ORCID	Institution/affiliation	Job title	Country	I want to participate actively in the output production of Research Software Definition
Morane Gruenpeter	Inria, Software Heritage	Software engineer and metadata specialist	France	Yes
Daniel S. Katz 0000-0001-5934-7525	University of Illinois	Chief Scientist, NCSA	USA	Yes
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Notes from 2nd meeting

1.1 The concept of an "inclusive" vs. "exclusive" definition

You can add aspects to the table or comment on the existing aspects.

Inclusive definition	Exclusive definition
Software that can be related to research	Software that is a product/result of research
Software products on which research depends on	Software that came from a research team in a research institution
Software used for data Data management	Software that is by itself a scientific/academic discovery
Both industrial/commercial and academic research may use/produce software to solve problems to benefit society.	Software that could be or was accepted to an academic journal (JOSS, IPOL, eLife)
Any software created for any research-related process	Software that was badged by a scholarly institution
Visualization software	Software that was reviewed in an academic evaluation
Software used to produce or process research data	Software that is innovative and is a major contribution to science or academia
Software that is intended to be used by the general public	Software created by tenured academics in aid of a research question
Software that is cited but it is currently obsolete	Software that has been created to answer a research question
Software that is intended for commercial purposes+1	Software that was created using research funds to be used in research
Software (script) that has been created to produce/visualize intermediate results in a paper (maybe -1)	The software <i>created</i> for research purposes by researchers (not the software <i>used</i> for research purposes)
	Software that is new and nobody has written something with similar purpose.
Software that is not currently usable (for any reason)	Software that is created for research in industry and the military

	Software that allows to answer scientific questions
	Research Software is also time bound, and intention bound.

Hinsen's software stack:

- (1) "...infrastructure created specifically for scientific computing, but not any particular domain."
- (2) "...domain specific research software. These are tools and libraries that implement models and methods which are developed and used by communities ranging in size from a single research lab to thousands of researchers"
- (3) "...software written by scientists for a specific research project...scripts, notebooks, and workflows, but also special-purpose libraries and utilities."

And then the paper also excludes layers that underpin all this:

- (4) "Infrastructure software that is not specific to scientific computing. ... compilers and interpreters, libraries for data management, but also higher level tools such as text editors and Web browsers. ... obtain[ed] from the wider non-scientific software market"
- (5) operating system
- (6) Hardware"

Name	In your opinion, which approach is better for a Research Software definition?	Where is the limit for software that should be FAIR? (you can choose a layer from Hinsen's software stack or describe a limit)
Morane	I'm leaning towards the exclusive approach for different reasons, first a pragmatic reason - having all software products FAIR is not realistic. Also, by choosing the exclusive approach we focus software which has an academic impact as a research discovery. It is like choosing to focus on diamonds, instead of requiring all stones to be FAIR. At the moment even the diamonds are not acknowledged in academia.	Hinsen's layers are a good example of required software for reproducibility, but it is impossible to say that layer 1 is research discovery and/ or a major contribution for science. I personally think that the limit should be on software that is identified by its creators as an academic discovery and that with this identification, the creators decide to add citation information and/or publish the software in an academic venue (which might be a journal, a research catalog/registry or an academic

		deposit - HAL, Zenodo or an Institutional Repository)
Dan	Exclusive - research software to me is software intended for research, not all software that is involved in research, which could be all software, making the definition useless.	Ideally all software should be FAIR, but only the top 2 layers are research software
Anna	Software being non-scientific infrastructure (as in Hinsen 2019) can be a crucial part of producing/reproducing research data making it part of the data provenance. In this aspect, in my opinion, FAIR principles for research software should provide a tool to assess the level of "FAIRness" of any software that is part of the provenance of research data. Thus, I'm leaning toward the inclusive approach.	Ideally, all software being part of the research data provenance should be FAIR. (In case Research Software is defined by the exclusive approach, are the FAIR research software principles intended to guide assessing "FAIRness" only of Research Software or of software that is part of the research process, too?)
Tom	Broadly Inclusive, but with some boundaries... in the long tail there is software which could be made FAIR, but which for various reasons will not be made FAIR. The boundaries would be more around representation or dissemination: source code through to instantiated software.	Scientific Infrastructure... but it might need a tighter definition. I'd probably be happier if it was based on (multi-)domain or discipline specific methods and models that are well accepted, possibly have multiple implementations (and need to be maintained, but often only have utility in the research sector)
Anne Claire	I would go more to the exclusive approach. Research software are meant to answer research/novel questions. However, as for any research products, research software may be "research" only for a given time.	The two first layers (Project specific code and domain-specific tools). But I am not sure about Scientific infrastructure (I maybe could include it too)
Paula	I would also go with the exclusive approach, because it serves a specific purpose in time.	From the Hinsen's diagram I would apply FAIR to the first 3 blocks in the diagram from the top: Project specific, Domain specific, and scientific infrastructure.
Daniel G	I lean towards exclusive, but to me the scripts done as part of a research paper are also research software.	Up to layer 4. The packages involved to deliver research software should be FAIR. When Dockerfiles are available, they should also become

		FAIR.

Tom's point: From the point of view of the FAIR principles, we can consider research software as software that is produced in the process of research. FAIR is applied at the point of production, when software is an output.

Dan: Looking at software from the point of view of citation or reproducibility might be different - both are looking at software when it is used, not when it is produced.

Tom: Yes, good point. Also, almost invariably and new software is likely to include the use of other software

1.2 Software examples to complete report's case study

Ipol example

The screenshot shows the IPOL Journal website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for HOME, ABOUT, ARTICLES, PREPRINTS, WORKSHOPS, NEWS, and SEARCH. The main title of the article is "An Analysis and Implementation of the Shape Preserving Local Histogram Modification Algorithm" by Jose-Luis Lisani. Below the title, there are tabs for "article", "demo", and "archive". A green banner indicates the publication date as 2018-12-07 and provides a BibTeX reference. The abstract describes the implementation of an algorithm for local contrast enhancement. A "Download" section offers full text manuscripts in PDF (low-res and standard) and source code in TAR/GZ format. A "Preview" section shows a low-resolution PDF thumbnail with a warning about compression artifacts. A Software Heritage ID box is also visible, providing a URL to the software's digital object identifier.

Figure 1: View of a publication on the IPOL Journal platform

Jose-Luis Lisani, *An Analysis and Implementation of the Shape Preserving Local Histogram Modification Algorithm*, *Image Processing On Line*, 8 (2018), pp. 408–434. <https://doi.org/10.5201/ipol.2018.236>

Question	IPOL publication answer	Was this question helpful to determine if the software is RS
Does the research result depend on the software?		

Would a researcher be expected to cite this software?		
Is the software created with a research or commercial purpose?		
Is the software primarily used for purposes outside of research?		
Is the software/code needed for reproducing data analysis/results? deliver research results?		
Is there a paper about the software?		
Is there a research result that is dependent on this software?		
Could the software be replaced with other software without affecting the research results?		
Was the software developed by a researcher? Or in an academic context?		
Was the software evaluated or reviewed as part of a research process? (ACM badge, peer review, research institution committee, etc.)		
Would a researcher be expected to cite this software?		

SciPy example

<https://www.scipy.org/>

The screenshot shows the swMATH registry entry for SciPy. At the top, there is a search bar and navigation links. The main content area includes a description of SciPy, a list of keywords for the software, a word cloud of related terms, a list of references in zbMATH (492 articles), and article statistics and filters.

SciPy
 SciPy (pronounced "Sigh Pie") is open-source software for mathematics, science, and engineering. It is also the name of a very popular conference on scientific programming with Python. The SciPy library depends on NumPy, which provides convenient and fast N-dimensional array manipulation. The SciPy library is built to work with NumPy arrays, and provides many user-friendly and efficient numerical routines such as routines for numerical integration and optimization. Together, they run on all popular operating systems, are quick to install, and are free of charge. NumPy and SciPy are easy to use, but powerful enough to be depended upon by some of the world's leading scientists and engineers. If you need to manipulate numbers on a computer and display or publish the results, give SciPy a try!

Keywords for this software

Python package, Python parameter estimation, Journal of Open Research Software, arXiv publication, Astrophysics, JOSS, arXiv_stat.ML, arXiv, arXiv_cs.LG, machine learning, convergence, arXiv_quant-ph, Python, software publication, Quantum Physics

References in zbMATH (referenced in 492 articles)
 Showing results 1 to 20 of 492. Sorted by year (citations) 20

1. Chaudhry, Jehanzeb H.; Collins, J. B.: textitAposteriori error estimation for the spectral deferred correction method (2021)
2. Karban, Pavel; Pánek, David; Orosz, Tamás; Petrášová, Iveta; Doležel, Ivo: FEM based robust design optimization with Agros and Ártap (2021)
3. Aguirre-Mesa, Andres M.; Garcia, Manuel J.; Millwater, Harry: MultiZ: a library for computation of high-order derivatives using multicomplex or multidual numbers (2020)
4. Alain Jungo, Olivier Scheidegger, Mauricio Reyes, Fabian Balsiger: pymia: A Python package for data handling and evaluation in deep learning-based medical image analysis (2020) arXiv
5. Allen, Henry R.; Plishnyk, Mariya: Mathematical modelling of auxin transport in plant tissues: flux meets signalling and growth (2020)
6. Ando, Alessia; Breda, Dimitri; Scarabel, Francesca: Numerical continuation and delay equations: a novel approach for complex models of structured populations (2020)
7. Andrew R. McCluskey, Tim Snow: uravu: Making Bayesian modelling easy(er) (2020) not zbMATH
8. Andrieux, Stephane; Baranger, Thouraya N.: Nonlinear Cauchy problem and identification in contact mechanics: a solving method based on Bregman-gap (2020)
9. Archis S. Joglekar, Matthew C. Levy: ViaPy: A Python package for Eulerian Vlasov-Poisson-Fokker-Planck

Article statistics & filter:
 Search for articles [input] [Clear]
 MSC classification / top
 Top MSC classes
 35 Partial differential...
 65 Numerical analysis
 68 Computer science
 76 Fluid mechanics
 92 Applications of...
 Other MSC classes
 Publication year
 2010 - today
 2005 - 2009
 2000 - 2004
 before 2000
 Chart: cumulative / absolute

Figure 2: SciPY entry in swMATH registry which shows an metadata about SciPY and the list of citations where SciPY was cited (492 articles) accessed on February 22, 2021 on <https://swmath.org/software/6293>

Question	swMath entry- SciPy answers	Was this question helpful to determine if the software is RS
Is the software created with a research or commercial purpose?	[PAM] Created with research purpose but used with both research + Commercial	[AF] I would not oppose research and commercial or maybe we should be more precise about what we mean by "research".

<p>Is the software primarily used for purposes outside of research?</p>	<p>[MG] [PAM] I would say yes with 80% certainty</p>	
<p>Is the software/code needed for reproducing data analysis/results? deliver research results?</p>	<p>yes</p>	
<p>Is there a paper about the software?</p>	<p>[PAM] yes multiple papers</p>	<p>[PAM] yes it is helpful to determine whether this is research software, but I don't think it should be a requirement. [DG] yes, because it means that the sw was the scope of research. [TH] This seems overly restrictive [AF] this is a bit "old" fashion and linked to how "researchers" are evaluated. However, there is always a need to communicate about the software (paper or any other communication).</p>
<p>Is there a research result that is dependent on this software?</p>	<p>[AN] yes</p>	<p>[TH] Any research result? If the software is a research result?</p>
<p>Could the software be replaced with other software without affecting the research results?</p>	<p>[PAM] yes, most of the functionality of this software can be translated to other programming languages</p>	<p>[TH] If I have access to the source code, or a detailed explanation of an algorithm, then in theory, any software could be re-implemented</p>
<p>Was the software developed by a researcher? Or in an academic context?</p>	<p>[PAM] scipy is an ecosystem thus it was developed by a community, and in research context</p>	<p>[TH] depends on the definition of "researcher"</p>
<p>Was the software evaluated or reviewed as part of a research process? (ACM badge, peer review, research institution committee, etc.)</p>	<p>[AF] review is usage of scipy by millions of users (better than an "old" fashion review).</p>	<p>[DG] Similar to next point</p>
<p>Would a researcher be expected to cite this software?</p>	<p>[PAM] yes that's why citation is provided</p>	<p>[DG] credit is the way authors claim their product is research</p>

Data visualisation in Excel example

“The Weissgerber et al. paper makes a good argument for shifting the default data visualisation from bar plots to dot plots that show more information about the data. They provide an Excel spreadsheet with a template for producing their preferred plots, and instructions for using GraphPad PRISM. But there are no instructions for making their dot plots using free and open source software, which limits the usefulness of the paper. R is a good free and open source choice to implement these plots because it produces high quality visualisations with relative ease. Making these plots in R also solves a few problems in the Excel spreadsheets provided by Weissgerber et al. For example:

- * The Excel spreadsheets are limited to 15-20 observations, (more than that requires some fiddling about), but the only limitation using R is the memory of your computer (so thousands to millions of observations should be no problem for most people).
- * Some of the plots in the Excel sheet don't have axis tick labels or axis labels. These are taken care of automatically with R code.
- * Note that the plotting functions in R can compute the medians for us, so we don't need any behind-the-scenes stuff like in the Excel spreadsheet.
- * Using R we can very easily change the axis labels by changing the text between the double quote marks in the xlab and ylab fields.”

<https://journals.plos.org/plosbiology/article/comment?id=10.1371/annotation/f159526e-8a40-43f3-8d3c-080b3bb6f5a3>

Comment posted by benmarwick on **02 Jun 2015 at 18:57 GMT**

Weissgerber TL, Milic NM, Winham SJ, Garovic VD. Beyond bar and line graphs: time for a new data presentation paradigm. PLoS Biol. 2015 Apr 22;13(4):e1002128.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.1002128>

Question	Microsoft Excel	Was this question helpful to determine if the software is RS
Is the software created with a research or commercial purpose ?		
Is the software primarily used for purposes outside of research?		
Is the software/code needed for reproducing data analysis/results? deliver research results?		
Is there a paper about the software ?		
Is there a research result that is dependent on this software?		
Could the software be replaced with other software without affecting the research results?		
Was the software developed by a researcher ? Or in an academic context ?		
Was the software evaluated or reviewed as part of a research process? (ACM badge, peer review, research institution committee, etc.)		
Would a researcher be expected to cite this software?		
Is the software created with a research or commercial purpose ?		
Is the software primarily used for purposes outside of research?		

[DG] In short, the macros would be RS, but not excel

Scala example

Figure 4: A combined figure from the first page of the first Scala publication (cited 782 times accessed on google scholar on February 22, 2021) and a diagram explaining scala
 Odersky, M., Altherr, P., Cremet, V., Emir, B., Maneth, S., Micheloud, S., ... & Zenger, M. (2004). An overview of the Scala programming language. Technical Report IC/2004/64

Question	Scala programming language	Was this question helpful to determine if the software is RS?
Does the research result depend on the software?		
Would a researcher be expected to cite this software?		

Is the software created with a research or commercial purpose?		
Is the software primarily used for purposes outside of research?		
Is the software/code needed for reproducing data analysis/results? deliver research results?		
Is there a paper about the software?		
Is there a research result that is dependent on this software?		
Could the software be replaced with other software without affecting the research results?		
Was the software developed by a researcher? Or in an academic context?		
Was the software evaluated or reviewed as part of a research process? (ACM badge, peer review, research institution committee, etc.)		
Would a researcher be expected to cite this software?		

1.3 The "chicken or the egg dilemma" of software in a scholarly infrastructure

1. Software in a scholarly infrastructure is Research Software
2. Research Software should be registered and deposited in a scholarly infrastructure

We might want to identify RS by its location and dissemination (in or by a scholarly infrastructure) but at the same time we want to tell software creators to use the scholarly infrastructures for their RS.

“Software that researchers in any discipline may feel the need to have **scholarly infrastructure support for**, no matter if it is considered a **tool**, a **result** or an **object of study**”

European Commission. Directorate General for Research and Innovation. (2020). Scholarly infrastructures for research software: report from the EOSC Executive Board Working Group (WG) Architecture Task Force (TF) SIRS. Publications Office. <https://doi.org/10.2777/28598>

Name	Should we use the software dissemination as a way to identify RS? Why? Why not?	Comments on answer
Morane		
Tom	No. If the FAIR principles drive policy, and policy drives what is or should be captured in scholarly infrastructure, then this criterion will end up being a circular definition.	
Anne	No (I put lots of non RS in zenodo...). The way we disseminate is linked to the funding of our work.	
Anna	No, but we might want to think about	

	whether software SHOULD be disseminated. In case it's not registered or disseminated, it might still be research software, but not FAIR.	
Daniel	<p>I think that software in specific code registries such as Zenodo is a good driver for determining whether it's RS or not. Namely because the authors ask for citation.</p> <p>Other code registries like ASCL, or the USGS registry only have research software in them. In those cases, YES.</p>	
Paula	<p>Not really, as long as it is findable and accessible, it shouldn't matter the location. Some research software like Python have their own registry which might not be scholarly. Here is the example: Python Package Index, has a special Science/Research category.</p>	

1.4 Bonus question: who is expected to apply FAIR?

- a. The researcher / software creator
- b. The research institution / software authority (copyright holder)
- c. The infrastructures holding the software (repositories, registries, publishers, aggregators)
- d. Other

Name	Who is expected to apply FAIR?	why?
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Daniel G	Researchers (creators)/adopters of software	To be able to build on the results from others
Anna	Everyone above plus the users	Users - in order to evaluate/choose the tools they use in their research
Paula	Software creators	for the benefit of software users or reusers
Anne Claire	Not the researchers or software creator as such but they would use tools/software (not RS) to support them. But definitely not the infrastructure either (because they do not have any information except if there were added somehow "automatically").	
Tom	All	<p>They have different roles and responsibilities.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creator: metadata (they know the software best) - Owner: policy obligations (funder obligations etc) - Infra: boundaries of service (what categories of metadata, what functionality like access/discovery methods)